

#4: Identifying climate change-driven tipping points in ecosystems and society

In addition to the potentially devastating impacts of climate tipping points on ecosystems and society, incremental climate change, through both gradual warming and extreme events, can trigger tipping points in ecological and social systems, such as biodiversity loss or the permanent displacement of people. To assess these risks, it is crucial to examine which local or large-scale climate conditions or exceedance of climate thresholds could lead to tipping in these systems.

Action

TipESM will advance knowledge on a range of ecosystems and societal systems at risk of tipping and identify the climate thresholds and drivers that may lead to tipping. TipESM will use a range of modelling approaches to investigate systems that are vulnerable, such as those with a limited ability to adapt. We will examine tipping points in three different terrestrial ecosystems, related to tropical rainforest-savanna ecosystems and mountain biodiversity. Additionally, we will identify thresholds for marine species and the conditions under which certain habitats would be lost. TipESM will further analyse social tipping points related to human displacement and poverty traps caused by climate-driven changes in extreme events.

Studying climate change-driven tipping points in ecosystems and society

TipESM will study climate change-driven tipping points in ecosystems and society by focusing on a range of individual ecosystems and investigating which local or large-scale climate conditions, or exceedance of climate thresholds, would lead to tipping in these ecosystems. TipESM will focus on terrestrial ecosystems in Sub-Saharan African forests and savannas, the Amazon rainforest, and mountain ecosystems, examining tipping processes by modeling changes in biomes, habitats, and species. We will also use simulations and reconstructions of past vegetation to understand what underlying processes and thresholds may lead to tipping. In marine ecosystems, TipESM will identify thresholds for species and habitats vulnerable to deoxygenation and acidification, focusing on the Pacific, Arctic, upwelling regions, and deep-sea habitats. We will further develop conceptual models for a fjord system in Greenland and identify thresholds at which gradual changes in ocean stratification and the retreat of marine-terminating glaciers lead to tipping in fish species. For social systems, TipESM will examine climate-driven displacement, exploring the impact of recurrent tropical cyclones on households in the Philippines and the implications of changing flood frequencies for human displacement. Thereby, we will address consequences for households that may become trapped in poverty and identify areas where temporary displacement could become permanent.

By focusing on climate change-driven tipping points in ecosystems and society, TipESM will:

- Assess the risk of tipping caused by incremental warming, associated climate change, and extreme events
- Identify the climate thresholds and drivers that may lead to tipping
- Evaluate changes in terrestrial and marine biomes, habitat and species loss, and tipping elements related to human displacement and poverty traps

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TipESM - Exploring Tipping Points and Their Impacts Using Earth System Models

TipESM brings together scientists from a range of disciplines to deliver a step change in our understanding of climate tipping points in the Earth system, including their impact on ecosystems and society, combined with a set of early warning indicators and safe future emission pathways that minimise the risk of exceeding such tipping points.

Expected impacts of TipESM

The key objectives of the project are to:

- Advance knowledge and solutions in Earth system science, pathways to climate neutrality, climate change adaptation, climate services, social science for climate action and understanding of climate-ecosystem interactions
- Contribute substantially to key international assessments (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, and the European Environment Agency)
- Increase the transparency, robustness, trustworthiness and practical usability of the knowledge base on climate and Earth system change for use by policymakers, practitioners, other stakeholders and citizens
- Strengthen the European Research Area with increased knowledge of the risks of crossing climate tipping points

Project partners and associated partners

- Danish Meteorological Institute
- Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
- The French National Centre for Scientific Research (and their affiliated entities)
- The Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
- University of Bergen
- The Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
- Barcelona Institute for Global Health
- University of Leeds
- Met Office UK
- University of Reading
- University of Liverpool
- University of Bern
- Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research

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UK Research and Innovation

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